

Development of a Laboratory Set-Up of a Horizontal Slinky-Loop Ground-Coupled Air-Conditioning System

H.F.R. Bosshard^{1,a}, M.C.E. Manuel^{2,b}, K.A.S. Baraquiel^{2,c}, J.J.P. Codia^{2,d}, C.A.L. Molina^{2,e}, J.R.R. Narceda^{2,f}, E.E. Zuñiga Jr.^{2,g}

¹*Far Eastern University Institute of Technology, Manila, Philippines*

²*Mapua University, Manila, Philippines*

^aCorresponding author: hrbosshard@feutech.edu.ph

^bmcemanuel@mapua.edu.ph

^ckarl.baraquiel22@gmail.com

^djonjhozecodia@gmail.com

^echarles17angelo@yahoo.com

^fjayjrn6@gmail.com

^gjunjun_zuniga@yahoo.com

Abstract. The ASHRAE-funded project, through the Undergraduate Program Equipment Grant, featured the use of a closed, horizontal loop ground-coupled air-conditioning system (GCACS). The project resulted in the construction of a physical laboratory set-up composed of a room that represented the built environment to be cooled, digital displays of conditions during operation, and two heat exchangers: the fan coil unit (FCU) installed inside the laboratory room and the high-density polyethylene pipe (HDPE) looped underground. The laboratory room had dimensions of 2.5m×2.5m×2.5m and was mainly made of concrete hollow blocks for the walls, metal sheet for the roof, and plywood for the ceiling. Sensors linked to digital displays measured temperature and relative humidity at various points in the system. The FCU was the main means for sensible heat to be rejected from inside the laboratory room. Tap water was used as the heat transfer medium intermittently flowing inside the closed-loop system. The underground heat exchanger was intended to facilitate the transfer of thermal energy from the medium to the soil. HDPE pipes were laid out at a depth of 1.52 m below the ground surface in a slinky coil configuration. Initial performance testing of the system was performed shortly after completion of construction.

INTRODUCTION

Numerous studies have pointed to the existence of climate change and linked global warming to destructive human activities. This has prompted various organizations worldwide to find a solution to the looming threat posed by increasing global temperature to human life on earth. Among the suggested solutions to help mitigate the negative impacts of human activity-related climate change include the use of 'greener' materials and processes, sustainable resource utilization, increasing process efficiencies, and trends towards 'net zero' operations, just to name a few.

HVAC systems are known to consume a significant portion (40% to 60%) of a building's energy requirement. In nations which still depend mostly on fossil fuels for energy production, HVAC systems indirectly account for the release of massive amounts of greenhouse gases to the environment. The environmental impact caused by the industry has prompted various organizations involved in HVAC technology (e.g. ASHRAE) to pursue initiatives that would reduce (or if possible remove) the harmful effects of HVAC technologies on the planet. Some of such initiatives involve innovations which may be more efficient than conventional technologies. A kind of innovation

that offers improved operating efficiency are ground source heat pumps (GSHP) or ground coupled air-conditioning systems (GCACS).

GCACS takes advantage of the natural temperature difference between above ground and underground conditions. During cold seasons, the temperature above ground is lower than that of the soil underground and vice versa during hot seasons. This phenomenon is made possible by the ability of soil to store and dissipate thermal energy and to resist heat transfer to and from the soil surface. The soil beneath the surface can thus act as a heat source during colder months and as a heat sink during warmer months. In tropical climates, GCACS are more useful to act as heat sinks due to the prevalence of higher surface temperature in most months of the year and the high volume of rain water that seeps into the earth, increasing the rate of heat dissipation of subsurface soil.

GCACS offer several advantages over conventional vapor compression systems. Some advantages include limited use of chemical refrigerants, limited use of compressors, and reduced maintenance and operating costs, to name some. One of the main disadvantages of GCACS, however, is the high capital requirement due to the expense required for drilling or excavation. In some configurations, the requirement for the use of land or a water body is also considered a disadvantage.

There is a very limited knowledge about GCACS in the Philippines. An online search of peer-reviewed academic journals would result in very few manuscripts that would involve GCACS research or application in the Philippines. One of the aims of this study, therefore, is to build knowledge and experience in designing and implementing GCACS in the Philippines. The main objective of the research project, however, is to develop a laboratory that mechanical engineering students may use to both complement their mechanical engineering education and become knowledgeable about an alternative technology to vapor compression-based systems.

METHODOLOGY

Overview of the Ground-Coupled Air-Conditioning System Laboratory

The developed laboratory is composed of the following main parts: heat exchangers (FCU and underground pipes), heat transfer medium (flowing water, pump, expansion tank), sensors (temperature and relative humidity sensors and visual display), electrical (controls and connections) and the laboratory structure. Fig. 1 shows the perspective view of the whole set-up of the laboratory.

FIGURE 1. Perspective view of the developed GCACS laboratory

Site Selection and Survey

Several sites were considered for the construction of the laboratory. However, only one of the sites qualified with the criteria used for selecting the location of the laboratory. Criteria that guided site selection were accessibility, security, cost, permit requirements, and ease of construction.

The site selected was located in Pines City Executive Village, Barangay San Roque, Antipolo City, Philippines. The site has the following profile: the site is in a tropical climate, has an average ambient temperature is 28.1 °C, and the months January and May have the lowest and highest average ambient temperature in a year, respectively. Surveys of the site resulted in gathering preliminary data about accessibility, ambient temperature, existing shadings, general soil type, the orientation of the laboratory room, and the possible options for the placement location of the laboratory equipment.

Laboratory Room Design and Construction

The laboratory room served as the simulated built environment of the system and housed a fan coil unit (FCU), a light bulb, and sensors (temperature and humidity). The room was constructed with a dimension of 2.5m×2.5m×2.5m. JETECH Engineering Technologies was contracted to perform the civil and electrical works. The construction period was from the fourth week of March 2017 until the second week of April 2017. The walls were made of reinforced concrete hollow blocks with cement and light colored paint (cream white) finishing for waterproofing and aesthetics. The roofing was made of corrugated sheet metal and was separated with an air gap from the ceiling made of plywood to reduce solar heat gain through the roof. Plywood and sheet metal were installed around the air gap to prevent animal intrusion. The room did not have windows but had a standard sized door made of wood, facing the SE direction.

Heat Load Calculation

Sensible heat load was the only heat load considered in the study thus latent heat load was neglected in the calculations. Considering existing shading, infiltration, solar heat gain, heat transfer from ambient air, design indoor temperature (27 °C) and internal heat gains (40W light bulb and FCU motor), the grand total heat load was estimated to be 1.24 kW. The calculated grand total heat load was used to calculate the volumetric flow rate of the cooling medium (tap water) in the FCU and the underground heat exchanger, the minimum required volumetric flow rate of air through the FCU, and the total length of the pipe that served as the underground heat exchanger.

Design and Installation of the GCACS

The main components of the GCACS are the following: piping system, water pump, FCU, expansion tank, and flow valve. Fig. 2 shows the schematic diagram of the GCACS. The cooling medium, transported through the whole system through pipes, is forced to flow by the water pump. An electric generator set provides the energy required to drive the pump. The flow rate is manually set by adjusting a globe valve installed at the discharge of the pump. The medium then enters the laboratory room and passes through the FCU and collects in the expansion tank (water tank). The medium is then induced to flow from the tank and through the underground pipes due to the pump suction. The different components of the GCACS are shown in Fig. 2.

FIGURE 2. Schematic diagram of the GCACS

The piping material used for the underground heat exchanger was high-density polyethylene (HDPE), as recommended in the literature due to its optimal characteristics i.e. high-pressure rating, good resistance to corrosion, and low cost. The relatively low thermal conductivity of HDPE would require a longer total pipe length to attain the desired heat rejection rate. Compression fittings were used to connect the HDPE pipes. The pipes exposed to the surroundings were insulated. The length of the pipe and the trench were calculated using equations 1 to 5.

$$L_l = \pi d_{loop} \quad (1)$$

$$N_l = \frac{L_{pipe} - \frac{\pi d_{loop}}{2} - d_{loop}}{Ll + 2P} \quad (2)$$

$$L_{trench} = Nl(P) + d_{loop} \quad (3)$$

$$L_{t-h} = \frac{L_{pipeTotal} - L_{pipe}}{2} \quad (4)$$

$$L_{trenchTotal} = L_{trench} + L_{t-h} \quad (5)$$

Where L_l is the length of the loop; d_{loop} is the loop diameter; N_l is the number of loops; L_{pipe} is the length of the pipe; $L_{pipeTotal}$ is the total pipe length; P is the pitch or spacing; L_{trench} is the length of the trench; L_{t-h} is the length of the basic trench to the header, and; $L_{trenchTotal}$ is the total length of the trench. L_{pipe} was estimated using heat transfer equations for pipes.

A 1.5 TR capacity chilled water FCU (Brand: Tosot, model: TWH18MC-D3DNA3D) was installed inside the laboratory to facilitate the heat transfer inside the room. The FCU was installed by a local contractor. The FCU was deliberately oversized in preparation for future research activities.

The water pump selected was a 0.55 kW centrifugal pump (Brand: CNP Pumps, model: CHLF[T]2-20) supplied by Powerry International Traders. The pump capacity was beyond what was required due to unavailability of a pump that could supply the computed flow rate and also in preparation for future research activities. A globe valve was used to restrict the flow rate of the medium. The flow rate of 8.316 L/min was maintained during trials.

The expansion tank (Brand: Bestank) was purchased from a local hardware. The 450-gallon tank served as a reservoir and was made of polyethylene. Insulation was installed on the outer surface of the tank. Fig. 3 shows the above-mentioned components of the GCACS.

FIGURE 3. Different components of the GCACS: (a) underground HDPE pipes in slinky configuration connected by compression fitting, (b) chilled water FCU, (c) centrifugal pump and manual valve, (d) expansion tank and insulated exposed piping.

Soil Excavation and Backfill

A U-shaped trench which served as the location for the underground heat exchanger was excavated. The trench had the following dimensions: 19 m length (outer length of the 'U', 8m length for each of the longer portions), 1.524 m depth, 1 m width, 1 m gap between long portions of the 'U.' the excavation was done manually by human laborers. The HDPE pipes were then laid and secured at the bottom of the trench. A leak test was conducted to ensure that no leaks were present in the connections. The trench was then backfilled manually. Fig. 4 shows the underground piping configuration and the trench excavation.

FIGURE 4. (a) Underground HDPE piping configuration and dimensions, (b) manual excavation of trench

Instrumentation and Display

Temperature and humidity sensors (Brand: generic model R8009 and R8022) were installed at various locations in the system. Thermometer sensors were installed at the inlet and outlet of the FCU, while the thermohygrometer sensors were installed inside at the center of the laboratory room and outside by the display panel. Fig. 5 shows the display panel and location of sensors.

FIGURE 5. (a) Digital display of temperature and humidity at various points in the system incorporated into schematic diagram, (b) location of sensors

Data Gathering

After completing the construction and final checks on individual components of the GCACS Laboratory, the system was operated as a whole. Data gathered to assess the effectiveness of the system were the following: inlet and outlet temperature of the cooling medium at the FCU and the dry bulb temperature both inside and outside the laboratory room. Data collection was done within three (3) days at varying times. Each data collection session lasted for two hours to avoid overheating the pump motor, and data was manually recorded every 10 minutes. Collected data were categorized according to the time the readings were recorded. The categories were morning (0600H to 1200H), afternoon (1200H to 1800H), and night (1800H to 0000H) sampling period.

Project Cost

The cost (in Philippines Peso, PHP) of the different parts of the project is shown in Table 1. The majority of the cost of the project was spent on the construction of the laboratory room, FCU supply and installation, and the supply and installation of the generator set and electrical components. The total cost of the project slightly exceeded the allocated ASHRAE grant of PHP 231,819.00 (USD 5,000) by PHP 6,325.45.

TABLE 1. Itemized cost of different parts of the project

Item	Cost (PHP)
High-Density Polyethylene Pipe	7,758.00
Construction Materials (Valves, fittings, etc.)	15,341.25
Generator Set and Labor	54,089.00
Fan Coil Unit	54,603.00
Pump	6,831.00
Construction of Laboratory Room	69,463.20
Instruments for testing (Humidity and Temperature Sensor)	1,760.00
Water Tank	6,300.00
Excavation	12,000.00
Miscellaneous	9,999.00
<i>Total</i>	<i>238,144.45</i>

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A summary of the temperature readings is shown in Table 2. The initial performance test of the geothermal system resulted in seemingly very little heat exchange occurring in the FCU and in the underground pipes. The highest temperature difference observed between the water leaving and entering FCU was only 1°C. This suggests that the soil surrounding the pipes may have stored a significant amount of thermal energy while it was still left in the open after the trench excavation and may have reduced capacity to serve as a heat sink. The stored thermal energy may not have significantly dissipated yet underground during the time of data collection. It was also observed that there were cases that the water leaving the FCU had a lower temperature than the water entering. This could either be caused by inaccurate sensors or the GCACS acting as a heat pump instead.

The temperature difference between the laboratory room and the outdoor surroundings fluctuated by up to 5°C. Trends for indoor and outdoor dry bulb temperature are shown in figure 6. Outdoor temperature fluctuated by as much as 7.3°C during the afternoon period. Based on the observed trend, the outdoor temperature can be seen to exhibit a lot of fluctuations within a 120 min sampling period and is observed to be highly dependent on the weather (cloudy, rainy, sunny, etc.). The temperature inside the room tended to be more consistent, with the highest range only at 2.7°C. Room temperature did not fluctuate as much as outdoor air temperature. It is interesting to note that the indoor temperature during most afternoon and night temperature data immediately decreased within 20 to 30 minutes after the GCACS is switched on. The indoor temperature then stabilized at a certain temperature with an average of 30.9°C and 32.5°C during morning and afternoon experiment trials, respectively. This may suggest that heat from both external and internal sources have been transferred through the heat exchangers, despite the very small temperature difference recorded across the FCU.

The design target of 27°C dry bulb temperature inside the room was never attained in all trials.

TABLE 2. Summary of temperature readings

Parameter	Summary of Recorded Temperature (°C) During Each Test Period											
	Morning N=5				Afternoon N=6				Evening N=1			
	Max	Min	Mean	σ	Max	Min	Mean	σ	Max	Min	Mean	σ
Indoor Temperature (T_i)	32.2	29.5	30.9	0.81	34.1	31.8	32.5	0.42	34.6	32.8	33.2	0.44
Outdoor Temperature (T_o)	35.0	28.3	31.9	1.85	35.4	28.1	32.2	2.28	31.0	28.7	30.3	0.73
Difference Between Outdoor and Indoor Temperature (T_{o-i})	3.3	-3.1	0.8	1.88	3.0	-5.0	-0.4	2.33	-2.2	-4.1	-2.9	0.69
FCU Inlet Temperature (T_{wi})	31.0	29.0	29.8	0.33	31.3	29.8	30.4	0.34	31.9	30.4	31.0	0.39
FCU Outlet Temperature (T_{wo})	30.6	29.1	29.9	0.35	31.3	30.3	30.7	0.25	31.3	31.1	31.2	0.07
Difference Between FCU outlet and inlet Temperature (T_{wo-wi})	0.8	-1.1	0.1	0.25	1.0	-0.4	0.3	0.22	0.8	-0.7	0.3	0.39

FIGURE 6. Trend of indoor and outdoor dry bulb temperature during (a) morning, (b) afternoon, and (c) night

CONCLUSION

A GCACS laboratory which was capable of real-time monitoring of system parameters was designed and implemented. The system featured the use of buried HDPE piping arranged in a horizontal slinky configuration to serve as the underground heat exchanger to transfer thermal energy from the laboratory room above ground to the soil below ground level. A laboratory room was also constructed to serve as the simulated built environment that the GCACS was designed to cool. Inside the laboratory room was a chilled water FCU which served as the venue for transferring heat from the room to the water flowing within the system. The whole set-up cost about USD 5136.85.

Preliminary data collection was conducted to test the performance of the system. However, the ability of the system to cool the indoor space to the desired temperature of 27°C was not achieved. Furthermore, the maximum temperature difference of the water flowing within the FCU achieved was only 1°C.

The seemingly poor performance of the GCACS may be attributed to several factors namely inaccurate sensors and displays, limited operation time (2 hours) for each test, and the heat sink (soil underground) still containing a significant amount of thermal energy due to the soil being exposed to surface conditions for about three days before backfilling-- the performance test was conducted within a week after the soil was backfilled into the trench.

RECOMMENDATIONS AND PLANNED FUTURE WORK

The authors plan to conduct advanced studies utilizing the GCACS laboratory. Some of the planned studies include simulation and validation of the system's operation, and upgrading of components of the laboratory (calibrated sensors, buried expansion tank, data loggers, and automatic control for pump operation).

The authors recommend the following to researchers who intend to develop their own GCACS laboratory in the future: install sensors underground to measure soil temperature, have a laboratory analyze the soil properties (e.g. porosity, soil type, conductivity, etc.) to produce a more accurate design, consider exploring other loop orientations (e.g. vertical), and to allocate considerable some time for the underground temperature to stabilize before conducting much rigorous system performance tests.

The project provided a great opportunity to the senior students who very actively took part in the planning, implementation, and testing of the system. Projects similar to this may be considered as an excellent capstone project which may involve multi-disciplinary teams of engineering students working together.

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